

Effect of solution concentration and deposition period on the properties of NiS₂ thin films

K. Anuar^{a*}, Z. Zainal^a, N. Saravanan^b and S. Nor Hamizi^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University Putra Malaysia, 43400 Serdang, Selangor, Malaysia

E-mail : anuar@fsas.upm.edu.my

^bFaculty of Engineering and Science, Universiti Tunku Abdul Rahman, 53300 Setapak, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

Manuscript received 21 November 2003, revised 7 February 2005, accepted 9 March 2005

Nickel sulfide thin films were deposited onto titanium substrates using triethanolamine as a complexing agent. The presence of the complexing agent was found to improve the lifetime of the deposition bath. The deposition conditions for obtaining good quality films such as solution concentrations and deposition period were optimized. The films were characterized using X-ray diffractometry and scanning electron microscopy. The photosensitivity of the films was studied using linear sweep voltammetry in the presence of sodium thiosulphate solution.

Conversion of sunlight directly to electricity using photo-voltaics or photoelectrochemical cells is a mean of generating electricity without causing changes to the environment because the fuel consumed is external to Earth¹. The main motivation for developing solar energy is the desire to get away from fossil fuels with their adverse effect on the environment^{2,3}. In recent years, the synthesis and characterization of metal chalcogenides of different groups have attracted considerable attention due to their brilliant application prospects. These compounds are used as sensor and laser materials, thin films polarizers and thermoelectric cooling materials⁴. They also possess certain criteria to make them potential candidates in photoelectrochemical solar cells.

Preparation of thin film metal chalcogenides by various methods and its different properties have been reported by many workers. The electrodeposition technique has been the most promising deposition method to grow metal chalcogenide thin films. In particular, for absorber films in solar cell, this technique is a perspective competitor because of several advantages such as the possibility for large-scale production, minimum waste of components and easy monitoring of the deposition process⁵. This technique is generally less expensive than those prepared by the capital-intensive physical methods. Binary chalcogenide with bandgap energy of about 0.95–1.2 eV, is an important semiconductor⁶. These compounds could display a variety of applications as essential material in photoelectrochemical solar cells to suppress the photocorrosion and to enhance the fill factor in electrical switches and in junction devices⁷.

Thin films of could also be used in memory switching devices⁸.

In this study, NiS₂ thin films were prepared using different solution concentrations and different deposition time.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1 shows the XRD plot for the films prepared using different concentration of Na₂S₂O₃. From the XRD data a peak at 2θ = 43.9° was obtained and identified as the NiS₂ peak. As the concentration of Na₂S₂O₃ was increased, the

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of the samples prepared at different concentration of Na₂S₂O₃ with constant Ni-TEA concentration : NiS₂(◆).

intensity of the peak corresponding to NiS_2 at 43.9° decreased. This indicates that higher $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ concentration prohibits the formation of good quality NiS_2 films. The film obtained using 0.0016 M $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ produced polycrystalline film as indicated from the XRD plot. The obtained data corresponds (Table 1) well to the Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards (JCPDS) data (File No : 11-99).

Table 1. Comparison of theoretical d -spacing value and experimentally obtained values for samples deposited at the different concentration of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$

Concentration (M)	2θ	d -spacing, \AA	
		Observed values	JCPDS values
0.016	43.9°	2.0	2.0
0.017	43.9°	2.0	2.0
0.018	43.9°	2.0	2.0
0.019	43.9°	2.0	2.0

Fig. 2 shows the SEM micrographs of NiS_2 films deposited at different $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ concentration. The films deposited at low $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ shows complete coverage over the surface of the substrate. No pinholes could be seen from the micrograph indicating complete surface coverage. The NiS_2 crystals were seen as trigonal shaped particles. The size of the crystallites varies from $2\text{--}3\ \mu\text{m}$. The crystal growths are uniform and compact. As the concentration of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ ($0.017\text{--}0.019\text{ M}$) increased, the formation of crystallites decreased. The surface of the substrate is not covered completely and the particles are smaller with the sizes varying from one another.

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs of films prepared using (a) 0.016 M , (b) 0.017 M , (c) 0.019 M $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ with constant concentration Ni^{2+} .

Fig. 3 shows the XRD plots of NiS_2 films deposited at different deposition time. As the deposition time was increased, the intensity of the peak corresponding to NiS_2 43.9° increased. The optimum deposition time for the film

Fig. 3. XRD pattern of the samples prepared at different deposition of time : $\text{NiS}_2(\diamond)$.

was found to be 60 min as the intensity of the peak is highest at this deposition time. The experimental values corresponding to NiS_2 matches well with the standard JCPDS values (Table 2). The SEM micrographs (Fig. 4) indicate that the surface of the substrate is not completely covered

Table 2. Comparison of theoretical d -spacing value and experimentally obtained values for samples deposited at varying different time d -spacing, \AA

Time (min)	2θ	d -spacing, \AA	
		Observed values	JCPDS values
15	43.9°	2.0	2.0
30	43.9°	2.0	2.0
45	43.9°	2.0	2.0
60	43.9°	2.0	2.0
75	43.9°	2.0	2.0

for deposition period of $15\text{--}45$ min. Upon 60 min of deposition time; the surface of the substrate is completely covered with polycrystalline material. The crystals indicate trigonal structure and the size varies from $3\text{--}4\ \mu\text{m}$. As the deposition time was increased to 75 min, the size of the crystals reduced. The surface of the substrate is not com-

pletely covered at this deposition time. The results obtained from SEM micrographs are well related to the data obtained from the XRD plot.

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs of films deposited for (a) 15 min, (b) 30 min, (c) 45 min, (d) 60 min and (e) 75 min.

The photoresponse for the NiS_2 films when illuminated with a tungsten-halogen lamp (100 W) shows the resulted changes in the current when the samples, employed as a cathode in the electrochemical cell, have been illuminated intermittently. This current change with the illumination confirms that the films possess semiconducting behavior. The fact that the photocurrent occurs on the negative (cathode) potential indicates that the films prepared are of *p*-type (positive) and they can be deployed as photo cathode in the PECs application to facilitate a reduction reaction of the electroactive species in the solution. During this process, the platinum electrode functions as the anode in the cell. The upper value corresponds to the current when the sample was illuminated (photocurrent), while the lower value corresponds to the dark-current, when the light was interrupted by chopping.

Experimental

The electrolyte bath consisted of NiSO_4 , TEA and $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$. The electrolyte was prepared using analytical grade reagents and distilled water. Electrodeposition was

performed in a conventional three-electrode cell. Ag/AgCl was used as the reference electrode to which all potentials were quoted. The working and counter electrodes were made from titanium (Ti) and platinum, respectively. The counter and working electrodes were polished prior to the insertion into the electrochemical cell. An Elchema potentiostat driven by model PS-605 Electrochemical Analysis System software was used to control the electrodeposition process and to monitor the current and voltage profiles. TEA was used to chelate with Ni^{2+} to obtain Ni-TEA complex. The presence of complexing agents such as TEA in aqueous solution was found to improve the lifetime of the deposition bath as well as the adhesion of the deposited film on the Ti substrate⁹.

The experiment was performed at room temperature (27°C) under N_2 blanket to remove any dissolved O_2 . The surface of the working electrode that should not be in contact with the electrolyte was sealed using PTFE tape. The films were deposited at -0.60 V using various $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ concentrations with a fixed concentration of Ni^{2+} (0.02 M) for ~1 h. The second experiment was carried out at different deposition time. The deposited films were rinsed with distilled water and kept for further analysis. X-Ray diffractometry (XRD) was carried out using Philips PM 1730 diffractometer with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$) for 2θ range from 2° to 60° . The obtained XRD patterns were matched with the Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards data (JCPDS). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed on a JEOL JSM 6400 Scanning Microscope. Photoelectrochemical (PEC) experiments were performed using $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ as electrolyte by performing linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) between -0.30 to -1.00 V. The sequence of constant illumination and chopping were performed on the PEC cell to study the effect on photoactivity behaviour. A tungsten-halogen lamp (100 W) was used for illuminating the electrode. The intensity of the light was maintained constant throughout the test.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank the Department of Chemistry, for the provision of laboratory facilities.

References

1. W. Wang, Y. Geng, Y. Qian, C. Wang and X. Liu, *Mater. Res. Bull.*, 1999, **34**, 403.
2. R. W. Birkmire, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, 2001, **65**, 17.
3. A. Goetzberger and C. Hebling, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, 2000, **62**, 1.

Anuar *et al.* : Effect of solution concentration and deposition period on the properties *etc.*

4. K. Zweibel, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, 2000, **63**, 375.
5. A. M. Fernandez and M. G. Merino, *Thin Solid Films*, 2000, **366**, 202.
6. J. John, B. Pradeep and E. Mathai, *J. Mater. Sci.*, 1994, **29**, 1581; J. P. Singh and R. K. Bedi, *J. Appl. Phys.*, 1990, **68**, 2776; P. Pramanik and S. Bhattacharya, *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.*, 1988, **7**, 1305; M. Sharon and K. Basavaswaran, *Solar Cells*, 1987, **20**, 323; D. T. Quan, *Thin Solid Films*, 1987, **149**, 197; R. D. Engelken, A. K. Berry, T. P. Van Doren, J. L. Boone and A. Shahnazary, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1986, **133**, 581.
7. P. Suguna, D. Mangalaraj, S. A. K. Narayandass and P. Meena, *Phys. Stat. Sol. (a)*, 1996, **155**, 405.
8. B. Subramanian, Mahalingam, C. Sanjeeviraja, M. Jayachandran and M. J. Chockalingam, *Thin Solid Films*, 1999, **357**, 119.
9. K. Anuar, Z. Zainal, M. Z. Hussein, N. Saravanan and I. Haslina, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cell.*, 2002, **73**, 351; Z. Zainal, N. Saravanan, K. Anuar, M. Z. Hussein and W. M. M. Yunus, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cell.*, (in press).